
Editorial

In Academia, there is hardly a more overlooked art form than animation. It is not because it is difficult to see it. Animation is everywhere. From preschooler online videos to military heads-up displays, the illusion of motion pervades societies, cultures, and minds.

Generations grew up watching Saturday Morning Cartoons while studios adapted tales and artists explored potential limits they could never find. Full-length movies gathered multitudes, clay pieces became alive, and computer graphics embraced the third dimension. With a flip book or a render farm, stories connected fans, and moving illustrations helped to educate, raise awareness, and practice.

The plurality of purposes and forms does not create boundaries. Animation invades other industries while reinventing its own. Characters and narratives also feature in books, comic books, video games, toys, and licensed products. Beautifully, animation also welcomes the opposite direction, giving motion to those created static.

One may ask why discussions are so few when animated arts are so many. We cannot answer that. But we can offer a solution.

The Journal of Animation Industries provides readers and writers a space for continuing discussion. Other (and excellent) journals share the area for academic studies. We are honored to join such a short list with the belief that it is not about taking someone's field of operation but broadening opportunities.

Many topics deserve attention and research to debate genres, themes, techniques, styles, languages, history, business models, applications, audiences, marketing, pipelines, distribution, and formats, among other factors that make animation thrive or fail. All of them potentially generate novel research questions and ground-breaking studies.

We see an academic gap to fill, which we now propose to start doing so. Our goal is to understand animation like never before and connect animated communities while doing it.

We know it is a long way that will change our perceptions and approaches. But as motion lovers, being stagnant has never been our way.

So, let's start our journeys together. One frame at a time.

Circle of Academic Studies in Creative Economies

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